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X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

Work Package WP4

Design of Mechanical Structure and Analysis

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Verification study

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO2 emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Deliverable details

This document provides a re-evaluation of the pile and cross-arm design considering their integration with the jacket and tower support structure presented by Silva (2014) due to the inclusion of the operation of the turbine until its shut-down speed of 25m/s.

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1 Introduction

The X-Rotor detailed design report, D4.3, proposes a reference support structure for the 2-bladed X-Rotor jacket and tower. For the reference design, the piles and cross-arm, previously designed for an operational wind speed up of up to 19m/s, were included as components.

This study presents a reassessment of the design of the 2-bladed X-Rotor foundations and cross-arm, while integrating these components on the total system composed by a rigid rotor, and the reference jacket and tower proposed by Silva (2024). Their design was updated for an operational wind speed up to 25m/s, the current shut-down speed of X-Rotor wind turbine.

2 Methodology

It was demonstrated in the detail design report by Silva (2024) that the most critical load case for the structural design was the lumped load case for the operational shut-down wind speed of 25m/s, lc23 from Table 1, where the review of the operational load cases is done. The coordinate system adopted for aerodynamic loads applied at the tower top for the design of jacket and tower is presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2. The extreme values of each component of the aerodynamic loads for the defined lumped load cases are presented in Table 2.

Figure 1 – Aerodynamic loads coordinate system for the case with wind orientation of 0 degrees – Adapted from Paraschivoiu (2002)

Figure 2 – Adopted coordinate system (a-b) Jacket

Table 1 Lumped operational load cases.

Load case ID	U_{inf} [m/s]	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	p [-]	ω [RPM]	θ_{upper} [deg]
LC1	< 3.5	-	-	0.10987	-	-
LC2	4	0.9	7.6	0.07745	2.5	2
LC3	5	1.1	7.4	0.09304	3.2	2
LC4	6	1.3	7.3	0.10274	3.8	2
LC5	7	1.5	7.3	0.10582	4.5	2
LC6	8	1.7	7.3	0.10249	5.1	2
LC7	9	2.0	7.3	0.09380	5.7	2
LC8	10	2.2	7.3	0.08136	6.4	2
LC9	11	2.5	7.3	0.06702	7.0	2
LC10	12	2.7	7.4	0.05249	7.6	2
LC11	13	3.0	7.5	0.03910	8.0	-9.8
LC12	14	3.3	7.6	0.02772	8.0	-14.2
LC13	15	3.6	7.7	0.01871	8.0	-14.6
LC14	16	3.9	7.8	0.01202	8.0	-15.0
LC15	17	4.2	8.0	0.00735	8.0	-15.6
LC16	18	4.6	8.1	0.00427	8.0	-16.2
LC17	19	4.9	8.3	0.00236	8.0	-16.9
LC18	20	5.2	8.5	0.00124	8.0	-17.6
LC19	21	5.6	8.6	0.00062	8.0	-18.4
LC20	22	6.0	8.8	0.00030	8.0	-19.1
LC21	23	6.3	9.0	0.00013	8.0	-19.8
LC22	24	6.7	9.2	0.00006	8.0	-20.8
LC23	> 25.0	-	-	0.00002	8.0	-21.1

Table 2 – Extreme values of aerodynamic load components at tower top

Load case ID	F_z [MN]		F_x [MN]		F_y [MN]		M_z [MNm]		M_x [MNm]		M_y [MNm]	
	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max
LC1	0.00	0.14	-0.09	0.07	0.00	0.00	-1.69	1.92	0.00	3.21	1.23	0.11
LC2	0.00	0.19	-0.12	0.09	0.01	0.02	-1.56	3.19	-0.03	4.35	1.69	0.04
LC3	0.00	0.30	-0.19	0.14	0.02	0.04	-2.44	4.98	-0.04	6.79	2.65	0.07
LC4	0.00	0.43	-0.27	0.20	0.02	0.05	-3.52	7.17	-0.06	9.78	3.81	0.10
LC5	0.00	0.58	-0.37	0.27	0.03	0.07	-4.79	9.76	-0.08	13.31	5.19	0.13
LC6	0.00	0.76	-0.49	0.35	0.04	0.09	-6.25	12.75	-0.10	17.38	6.78	0.17
LC7	0.00	0.96	-0.62	0.44	0.05	0.12	-7.91	16.13	-0.13	22.00	8.58	0.22
LC8	0.00	1.18	-0.76	0.55	0.07	0.15	-9.77	19.92	-0.16	27.16	10.59	0.27
LC9	0.00	1.43	-0.92	0.66	0.08	0.18	-11.82	24.10	-0.19	32.86	12.82	0.32
LC10	0.00	1.70	-1.09	0.79	0.10	0.21	-14.06	28.68	-0.23	39.11	15.25	0.38
LC11	-0.13	1.91	-0.78	1.61	-0.97	-0.84	-76.18	7.33	-17.00	53.31	13.21	4.36
LC12	-0.25	2.03	-0.60	2.01	-1.31	-1.12	-110.13	2.15	-40.09	60.64	15.10	2.13
LC13	-0.28	2.11	-0.53	2.19	-1.34	-1.01	-120.88	0.28	-56.94	64.65	17.78	1.14
LC14	-0.32	2.11	-0.55	2.36	-1.37	-0.89	-131.41	0.14	-70.22	67.14	18.62	-0.66
LC15	-0.37	2.07	-0.58	2.54	-1.43	-0.80	-143.34	0.53	-78.29	66.30	17.71	-2.73
LC16	-0.43	2.17	-0.61	2.71	-1.49	-0.74	-155.93	1.07	-85.87	64.24	18.90	-4.43
LC17	-0.49	2.27	-0.64	2.88	-1.56	-0.69	-169.68	1.79	-94.94	59.85	20.77	-5.78
LC18	-0.55	2.38	-0.67	3.05	-1.63	-0.65	-188.03	2.24	-103.31	53.75	22.87	-7.24
LC19	-0.60	2.50	-0.69	3.20	-1.69	-0.61	-203.61	2.90	-112.78	51.33	25.17	-8.90
LC20	-0.65	2.63	-0.72	3.33	-1.75	-0.57	-220.15	3.38	-121.93	44.96	27.96	-10.55
LC21	-0.70	2.76	-0.74	3.42	-1.83	-0.54	-235.62	3.81	-131.39	43.30	31.06	-12.21
LC22	-0.74	2.89	-0.75	3.56	-1.94	-0.50	-249.17	4.21	-140.78	38.81	34.31	-14.04
LC23	-0.79	3.01	-0.78	3.68	-2.04	-0.47	-261.36	4.67	-148.48	38.73	37.32	-16.00

From Table 2, it is possible to observe that load case lc23 generates the higher aerodynamic loads on the tower top. The maximum absolute thrust force (wind direction), F_z , and overturning moments, M_z , and M_x , are summarized in Table 3 and highlighted in Figure 3. The power production for the operational load cases is shown in Figure 4.

Table 3 – Tower top absolute maximum thrust and overturning moments for lc23 (U = 25m/s)

F_z [MN]	F_y [MN]
3.01	-2.04
M_z [MNm]	M_y [MNm]
-261.36	37.32

Figure 3 – Tower top thrust and overturning moments

Figure 4 – X-Rotor power production – Adapted from Ajay (2022)

Cross-arm

For the review of the design of the cross-section arm, the aerodynamic provided by Ajay (2022) were decomposed on components to be applied at the tips of the cross-arm. Here, only the normal force component were considered based on the assumption that the secondary rotors generated thrust would balance the tangential components of the aerodynamic loads. Figure 5. Illustrates the load decomposition where the blade roots’ resultant of the aerodynamic components of the normal force are applied to the cross-arm tips.

Figure 5 – Decomposition of blades normal forces

Figure 6 illustrates the load cycle for the vertical component of the blade 1 normal force, F_{NV1} , the horizontal component of the normal force, F_{NH1} , and the flap moment generated at the blade root due to the effect of the normal force distributed on the blade 1 span-wise, M_{Flap1} .

Figure 6 – Aerodynamic load components from normal force applied at the cross-arm tip.

Foundations

It was shown in Silva (2024) that the most loaded pile was pile2, that follows the leg numbering indicated in **Error! Reference source not found.** The pile follows its own coordinate system where the X-axis follows the direction of the pile shaft and the positive sign set from the mudline to the pile tip, so negative force values indicate compressive forces on the pile shaft. Table 4 shows the maximum and minimum values of the axial forces on each of the piles’ head for the lc23 when using, demonstrating that for this load case, pile 2 keeps being the most loaded pile and its loads can be used for the foundation design.

Figure 7 – Pile ID

Table 4– Extreme vertical force component on the pile head at the lower end of the fixed-based jacket legs

Pile_ID	$N_{x,max}$, [MN]	$N_{x,min}$, [MN]
1	-10.04	-36.35
2	-6.82	-40.06
3	-0.93	-27.63
4	3.02	-30.50

3 Results and discussion

Jacket

The final design for reference jacket for the 2-bladed X-Rotor wind turbine was presented by Silva (2024). The results from the fatigue and ultimate limit states of the jacket connections are presented in Table 10 of Appendix B with respect to the fatigue damage of the connections described that are illustrated in terms of the nodes and the connected beams, described in Figure 19 and Figure 20 of Appendix B.

The final jacket node’s position can be found in Appendix B, while a review from the jacket and tower cross-sections are shown in Appendix A.

Tower Top displacement

The softening effect of including the piles on the structural model can be seen on the shift of the natural frequencies of the system. While the first natural frequency of the system with a rigid rotor and jacket

clamped bottom connection is 0.98 Hz, and when the piles are considered, the first natural frequency is reduced to 0.65 Hz.

This effect can also be observed by the tower top lateral displacement, shown in Figure 8. The maximum lateral displacement for the clamped-bottom case is of 10.4 cm, while the maximum lateral displacement for the same case including the piles is 30 cm.

Figure 8 – Tower top displacement over one rotor rotation for a wind speed of 25m/s and different jacket bottom connections

System torsion mode

The X-Rotor turbine emergency breaking was investigated Silva (2024), where it was concluded that the resultant fatigue damage generated during the breaking of the turbine along its life-time is insignificant in comparison to the fatigue damage caused by the large cyclical loads generated by the operational aerodynamic forces. A jacket torsional mode shape, Figure 9, was observed at a frequency of 3.75 Hz when only the tower and the jacket with a clamped bottom connection are considered. The power spectrum density of the response of the critical jacket connection loads for the operational wind speed of 12m/s shows that the system does not show a considerable response on the torsional frequency.

$f_5 = 3.75 \text{ Hz}$

Figure 9 – Torsional jacket-tower mode shape

Figure 10 – Power spectrum response of axial force response from the critical connection at the jacket's leg bottom for lc11 (U = 13m/s)

Foundations

The pile design was updated to according to the load cases lc23 of Table 1. The assessment of the ultimate pile capacity of the pile is described in the detail design report, Silva (2024). It sets the minimum contact surface area between the pile and the soil for the loads to be transmitted to the soil throw the shaft friction and pile tip capacity indicates. When considering a pile diameter of 3m and an open bottom end, the minimum pile length of 22m is required to satisfy the ultimate pile capacity when considering the maximum absolute axial loading on pile 2, shown in bold in Table 4.

As described in the detail design, the lateral displacements of the piles should be limited up to 1% of the pile diameter to avoid loss of the pile support due to the soil degradation. Thus, the first 10m of pile below the mudline have a thicker cross section in order to provide more bending stiffness where the pile to most solicited laterally. Below the 10m mark, the pile has a constant cross section. The pile cross-section values are shown in Table 5. The trajectories of each pile over one rotor rotation for the wind speed of 25m/s are illustrated Figure 11, where the 1% D limit for the lateral displacement was respected for all piles.

Figure 11 – Piles’ head lateral displacement

Table 5 – Piles cross-section values

Pile range below mud-line	D, [m]	T, [cm]
0 -10m	3.0	14.5
-10m -50m	3.0	5.0

It can be noted that the cross sections below -10m are maintained from the detailed design report, while the upper sections from 0m to -10m below the mudline could be reduced even through a more critical cyclical loading from the wind speed of 25 m/s was considered. This was possible due to a better utilization of the fatigue damage utilization ratio. The fatigue utilization ratios of cross-sections at different heights along the pile are indicated in Figure 12. One can notice that from the cross section located at -50m and below, no significant fatigue damage can be observed. This illustrated that at this depth, the cyclical loading from the structure was already dissipated by the upper most integration with the soil. When observing the vertical displacement along the pile shaft, shown in

Figure 13, it can be noted that at the depth of -50 m, the vertical displacement of 0.3mm is very reduced, which demonstrated that at this depth the pile no longer solicites resistance from the soil. However, it is possible to see that the ultimate pile capacity that only access the external area without considering the flexibility of the pile returns a non-conservative value for the pile length. The ultimate stress of 38 MPa, considering a load factor of 1.25, was observed of the pile head section at the mudline.

Figure 12 – Fatigue damage utilization of 8 hotspot around the pile length cross-sections for critical pile

Figure 13 – Vertical displacement along pile 2 for lc23 with wind and wave directionality of 0 deg

The influence of the piles length on the system natural frequency was investigated. The reference structure suggested by Silva (2024) has a pile of 140m length, where the bottom most cross sections were proved to do not contribute to the load transfer to the soil. As discussed on this report, the load transfer occurs of the sections up to 50m below the mudline. Thus, the final length of the piles was reduced to 50m. After the redesign of the uppermost 10m of the piles and reduction of the piles’ length, the first natural frequency of the system 0.65Hz (for a 140m pile) was affected by just a small amount, ending up in 0.63 Hz. This value still sits on the safe range from the aerodynamic load excitation of 4p+5% of 0.56 Hz and 6P-5% of 0.76 Hz.

Cross-arm

After the cross-arm being evaluated for the critical load case, lc23, considering the higher cyclical loads generated by a wind speed of 25 m/s, its cross sections were updated with respect to the presented values previously described in Silva (2024). The cross-section dimensions are presented in Table 6.

Table 6 - Cross arm tapered cross-sections

Section	D, [m]	T, [cm]
Mid-section	6.9	12.5
Tip-section	6.5	10.0

The fatigue damage utilization ratios for 8 hot spot stresses around the mid-section and on the tip-section are shown in Figure 14. The same figure also indicates the location of the hot spots, as well as the coordinate system adopted on the cross-arm design. The increase of the cross-arm section caused a slight reduction on the first natural frequency of the system considering the updated piles, which assumes a final value of 0.57 Hz – still inside of the safe range between the excitation aerodynamic loads harmonics of 4p+5% and 6P-5%.

Figure 14 – Cross-arm’s fatigue damage utilization ratios for lc23

It can be observed that the hot sport 3 and 7 are the critical ones for the design of the cross-arm in terms of fatigue damage. This is due the large cycles from bending moment, M_y , resultant from the aerodynamic loads that can be seen in Figure 15 for the wind speed of 25m/s.

Figure 15 – Loading on cross-arm mid-section of lc23 (U=25 m/s)

The ultimate stress for hotspot 3 of the mid and tip-sections considering a load factor of 1.25 are presented on Table 7.

Table 7 – Ultimate stress on cross arm sections for lc23.

Section	HSS, [MPa]
Mid-section	118.0
Tip-section	94.4

The trajectory observed by the tip of the cross-arm attached to blade1 over one rotor rotation for a wind speed of 25m/s is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16 – Cross-arm tip displacement on ZY plan

It was demonstrated by Silva (2024) that the cross-arm consumes power during the turbine operation due to the drag forces acting over the cylindrical profiles. The increase of the cross-arm diameter to satisfy the fatigue damage safety requirements for up to a wind speed of 25m/s would increase this undesired effect. However, an alternative to mitigate the power loss due to an increased cross section is the use of fairings. This outer structure with a more efficient aerodynamic profile and without structural function could be attached to the cross-arm so that the drag forces acting over the cross-arm are reduced.

4 Conclusions

This report re-evaluated the design of the X-Rotor foundations and cross-arm when these components are integrated in the total system composed by a rigid rotor and the reference tower and jacket suggested by Silva (2024). The design of these components was updated such that they could satisfy the fatigue damage and ultimate stress requirements for up to a wind speed of 25m/s, demonstrated to be the most critical for the structural design.

The piles upper most 10m section had its wall thickness reduced to improve the fatigue damage utilization. The piles length could be reduced to 50m after it was demonstrated that the lower sections from the previous design do not contribute to the transmission of loads to the soil. The cross-arm sections were increased to satisfy the fatigue damage utilization limit. The increase of the power loss due to the additional aerodynamic drag forces acting on the cross-arm could be mitigated using fairings. The alternative to improve the aerodynamic profile of the cross arm requires further study.

The design changes made in this study did not compromise the system first natural frequency as the final value of 0.57Hz that still falls inside the safe ranges in between the loads harmonics of 4p+5% and 6P-5%.

It was also demonstrated that the torsional mode shape is not excited during operational, as the first torsional natural frequency is considerably higher than the most prominent aerodynamic load harmonics of 2P, 4P and 6P.

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Appendix A – Cross section dimensions

Figure 17 – Jacket cross-section reference ID

Table 8 Jacket Cross Section dimensions

Cross-section ID	Diameter [m]	Thickness [m]
CS1	2.2	0.137
CS2	2.2	0.137
CS3	1.32	0.0825
CS4	1.32	0.0825
CS5	0.924	0.082
CS6	0.924	0.082
CS7	2.2	0.137
CS8	2.2	0.137
CS9	1.32	0.0825
CS10	1.32	0.0825
CS11	0.66	0.04125
CS12	0.66	0.04125
CS13	2.2	0.137
CS14	2.2	0.137
CS15	1.32	0.0825
CS16	1.32	0.0825
CS17	0.66	0.04125
CS18	0.66	0.04125
CS19	2.2	0.137
CS20	2.2	0.137
CS21	1.32	0.0825
CS22	1.32	0.0825
CS23	0.792	0.0495
CS24	0.792	0.0495
CS25	2.2	0.137
CS26	1.32	0.0825
CS27	0.66	0.04125

Figure 18 – Tower cross-section reference

Table 9 - Tower cross-section dimensions

Cross-section ID	Diameter [m]	Thickness [m]
CS1	10.5	0.115
CS2	9.83	0.110
CS3	9.16	0.100
CS4	8.5	0.095

Appendix B - Nodes and beams reference ID

Figure 19 – Jacket node reference numbering

Figure 20 – Jacket beam reference numbering

The Table 10 shows the detailed results for the reference jacket structure suggested by Silva (2024). Nodes 1-4, 61-64 belong to the is foundation grouted connection and, thus, their results are not included in Table 10. Similarly, nodes 41-44 and 169-176, as these belong to the connection with the rigid transition piece.

Table 10 – Jacket connections damage and maximum stress

Node ID	Beam ID	Damage [-]	Max stress [MPa]
5	5	0,278	55,2
5	9	0,272	53,1
5	77	0,068	35,6
5	84	0,101	45,8
6	6	0,085	58,0

6	10	0,084	55,9
6	78	0,035	48,8
6	79	0,010	38,1
7	7	0,178	63,0
7	11	0,177	61,1
7	80	0,049	46,8
7	81	0,038	48,8
8	8	0,088	48,9
8	12	0,088	47,4
8	82	0,014	38,3
8	83	0,040	43,2
9	9	0,311	54,8
9	13	0,257	50,8
9	85	0,277	50,0
9	92	0,491	73,2
10	10	0,098	57,7
10	14	0,082	53,8
10	86	0,190	76,8
10	87	0,027	58,5
11	11	0,194	61,4
11	15	0,157	58,9
11	88	0,211	60,4
11	89	0,134	70,1
12	12	0,100	48,8
12	16	0,080	47,7
12	90	0,045	51,1
12	91	0,191	59,4
13	21	0,135	44,6
13	25	0,120	44,5
13	93	0,021	33,0
13	100	0,003	34,9
14	22	0,034	46,8
14	26	0,032	46,5
14	94	0,001	35,1
14	95	0,017	35,2
15	23	0,104	62,6
15	27	0,094	62,8
15	96	0,006	46,1
15	97	0,008	45,1
16	24	0,040	43,5
16	28	0,036	43,9
16	98	0,005	35,9
16	99	0,003	36,3
17	25	0,101	41,7
17	29	0,089	40,9
17	101	0,023	36,9
17	108	0,033	42,2
18	26	0,025	44,0
18	30	0,024	43,3
18	102	0,011	45,4
18	103	0,004	37,5

19	27	0,077	61,1
19	31	0,071	61,0
19	104	0,026	53,6
19	105	0,020	55,6
20	28	0,031	42,3
20	32	0,028	42,2
20	106	0,007	38,4
20	107	0,009	39,2
21	37	0,056	33,4
21	41	0,053	32,4
21	109	0,024	35,0
21	116	0,009	26,2
22	38	0,015	36,0
22	42	0,015	35,2
22	110	0,002	32,6
22	111	0,012	39,9
23	39	0,044	52,3
23	43	0,043	51,8
23	112	0,009	54,9
23	113	0,014	53,0
24	40	0,019	36,8
24	44	0,017	36,4
24	114	0,007	41,4
24	115	0,005	39,3
25	41	0,047	33,8
25	45	0,042	31,3
25	117	0,028	35,8
25	124	0,052	45,7
26	42	0,014	36,0
26	46	0,013	33,8
26	118	0,020	49,2
26	119	0,004	37,1
27	43	0,037	52,1
27	47	0,033	51,3
27	120	0,036	53,3
27	121	0,024	56,4
28	44	0,016	36,0
28	48	0,015	34,9
28	122	0,008	39,1
28	123	0,015	40,2
29	53	0,043	29,8
29	57	0,040	28,3
29	125	0,020	30,4
29	132	0,006	18,7
30	54	0,012	32,4
30	58	0,012	31,3
30	126	0,001	27,4
30	127	0,011	34,9
31	55	0,035	50,4
31	59	0,032	49,7
31	128	0,007	50,4

31	129	0,011	48,8
32	56	0,014	34,8
32	60	0,014	34,3
32	130	0,006	37,2
32	131	0,004	35,2
33	57	0,038	30,3
33	61	0,032	27,4
33	133	0,026	33,2
33	140	0,057	44,0
34	58	0,014	32,8
34	62	0,011	30,0
34	134	0,024	47,4
34	135	0,003	35,6
35	59	0,030	50,4
35	63	0,025	48,3
35	136	0,040	54,6
35	137	0,025	57,8
36	60	0,012	34,3
36	64	0,011	32,6
36	138	0,009	39,8
36	139	0,015	38,5
37	69	0,047	27,9
37	73	0,046	27,1
37	141	0,012	25,5
37	148	0,007	22,8
38	70	0,020	31,4
38	74	0,019	30,8
38	142	0,002	23,5
38	143	0,005	28,0
39	71	0,034	50,8
39	75	0,031	51,1
39	144	0,007	44,8
39	145	0,008	44,4
40	72	0,016	32,4
40	76	0,015	32,7
40	146	0,004	31,7
40	147	0,003	29,0
45	229	0,012	33,3
45	230	0,007	39,6
45	237	0,002	22,5
45	238	0,021	42,4
46	231	0,004	30,4
46	232	0,002	24,0
46	239	0,001	23,9
46	240	0,009	25,2
47	233	0,001	17,0
47	234	0,001	19,0
47	241	0,001	18,0
47	242	0,002	23,0
48	235	0,012	32,4
48	236	0,009	39,5

48	243	0,003	23,6
48	244	0,020	42,0
49	245	0,013	32,4
49	246	0,013	58,0
49	253	0,002	30,5
49	254	0,033	42,0
50	247	0,003	45,7
50	248	0,006	38,6
50	255	0,001	18,2
50	256	0,008	41,6
51	249	0,002	36,2
51	250	0,001	32,7
51	257	0,000	14,4
51	258	0,005	32,3
52	251	0,010	33,0
52	252	0,010	57,1
52	259	0,002	29,9
52	260	0,024	42,2
53	261	0,036	48,7
53	262	0,022	56,1
53	269	0,003	29,4
53	270	0,070	55,0
54	263	0,012	43,2
54	264	0,006	35,3
54	271	0,001	22,2
54	272	0,025	39,0
55	265	0,002	22,9
55	266	0,003	26,0
55	273	0,000	13,2
55	274	0,006	25,5
56	267	0,026	48,7
56	268	0,017	55,8
56	275	0,003	29,0
56	276	0,052	54,7
57	277	0,003	27,6
57	278	0,009	43,3
57	285	0,001	25,7
57	286	0,006	37,1
58	279	0,001	31,5
58	280	0,004	24,7
58	287	0,001	16,2
58	288	0,001	27,7
59	281	0,000	25,5
59	282	0,000	21,4
59	289	0,000	10,8
59	290	0,000	23,5
60	283	0,003	28,4
60	284	0,007	41,9
60	291	0,001	24,7
60	292	0,006	37,1
65	13	0,824	39,5

65	17	0,824	39,5
66	14	0,256	41,9
66	18	0,256	41,9
67	15	0,519	48,7
67	19	0,519	48,7
68	16	0,256	38,1
68	20	0,256	38,1
69	17	0,415	35,5
69	21	0,415	35,5
70	18	0,110	37,5
70	22	0,110	37,5
71	19	0,345	51,7
71	23	0,345	51,7
72	20	0,130	35,8
72	24	0,130	35,8
73	29	0,367	33,0
73	33	0,367	33,0
74	30	0,098	35,0
74	34	0,098	35,0
75	31	0,291	49,8
75	35	0,291	49,8
76	32	0,117	34,3
76	36	0,117	34,3
77	33	0,260	27,5
77	37	0,260	27,5
78	34	0,073	29,8
78	38	0,073	29,8
79	35	0,209	43,8
79	39	0,209	43,8
80	36	0,088	30,3
80	40	0,088	30,3
81	45	0,187	25,8
81	49	0,187	25,8
82	46	0,060	27,8
82	50	0,060	27,8
83	47	0,151	42,6
83	51	0,151	42,6
84	48	0,065	29,0
84	52	0,065	29,0
85	49	0,194	24,8
85	53	0,194	24,8
86	50	0,055	26,9
86	54	0,055	26,9
87	51	0,152	41,8
87	55	0,152	41,8
88	52	0,065	28,8
88	56	0,065	28,8
89	61	0,150	22,7
89	65	0,150	22,7
90	62	0,054	24,9
90	66	0,054	24,9

91	63	0,115	40,4
91	67	0,115	40,4
92	64	0,051	26,7
92	68	0,051	26,7
93	65	0,186	22,9
93	69	0,186	22,9
94	66	0,072	25,8
94	70	0,072	25,8
95	67	0,135	41,9
95	71	0,135	41,9
96	68	0,061	26,9
96	72	0,061	26,9
97	77	0,011	54,0
97	221	0,179	124,5
98	78	0,010	56,5
98	221	0,160	132,2
99	79	0,013	57,2
99	222	0,231	129,4
100	80	0,013	57,8
100	222	0,216	131,4
101	81	0,007	61,6
101	223	0,094	139,4
102	82	0,008	57,4
102	223	0,105	129,4
103	83	0,012	50,1
103	224	0,216	116,5
104	84	0,011	56,1
104	224	0,199	131,4
105	85	0,060	20,2
105	157	0,285	30,3
106	86	0,059	33,2
106	158	0,287	49,1
107	87	0,022	26,4
107	159	0,097	39,2
108	88	0,021	19,9
108	160	0,099	30,2
109	89	0,010	19,5
109	161	0,053	29,8
110	90	0,011	19,2
110	162	0,053	29,1
111	91	0,079	21,8
111	163	0,373	32,8
112	92	0,076	33,4
112	164	0,383	49,3
113	93	0,009	16,7
113	165	0,035	23,8
114	94	0,011	26,7
114	166	0,042	38,0
115	95	0,003	20,2
115	167	0,011	29,1
116	96	0,005	17,9

116	168	0,018	26,1
117	97	0,002	16,8
117	169	0,010	24,2
118	98	0,001	15,4
118	170	0,006	22,8
119	99	0,008	17,2
119	171	0,029	24,5
120	100	0,011	26,0
120	172	0,042	37,0
121	101	0,014	20,8
121	173	0,180	43,8
122	102	0,021	33,9
122	174	0,258	67,7
123	103	0,004	26,6
123	175	0,049	54,3
124	104	0,010	23,4
124	176	0,115	48,6
125	105	0,002	23,1
125	177	0,031	48,3
126	106	0,001	20,5
126	178	0,022	43,3
127	107	0,011	19,9
127	179	0,129	42,3
128	108	0,017	33,7
128	180	0,198	67,3
129	109	0,035	23,7
129	181	0,555	44,8
130	110	0,018	24,9
130	182	0,237	51,7
131	111	0,018	18,7
131	183	0,275	40,1
132	112	0,005	18,6
132	184	0,064	39,8
133	113	0,002	13,3
133	185	0,022	28,3
134	114	0,003	13,1
134	186	0,054	28,3
135	115	0,025	23,9
135	187	0,372	45,3
136	116	0,016	24,9
136	188	0,220	51,7
137	117	0,042	25,1
137	189	0,526	49,4
138	118	0,044	34,7
138	190	0,629	70,7
139	119	0,012	26,6
139	191	0,145	54,9
140	120	0,016	20,9
140	192	0,224	45,3
141	121	0,003	19,4
141	193	0,043	43,1

142	122	0,003	17,8
142	194	0,045	39,2
143	123	0,033	24,9
143	195	0,424	48,9
144	124	0,034	34,7
144	196	0,500	70,4
145	125	0,046	22,5
145	197	0,711	41,7
146	126	0,039	29,4
146	198	0,518	57,5
147	127	0,018	22,1
147	199	0,296	44,5
148	128	0,012	17,3
148	200	0,146	34,9
149	129	0,003	12,7
149	201	0,044	25,0
150	130	0,003	12,8
150	202	0,045	27,3
151	131	0,033	22,6
151	203	0,486	41,8
152	132	0,030	29,1
152	204	0,386	56,8
153	133	0,009	15,3
153	205	0,061	26,6
154	134	0,029	30,1
154	206	0,233	50,7
155	135	0,001	22,0
155	207	0,008	37,3
156	136	0,014	20,0
156	208	0,108	34,6
157	137	0,002	20,8
157	209	0,016	36,4
158	138	0,001	17,0
158	210	0,006	29,7
159	139	0,008	15,0
159	211	0,063	26,2
160	140	0,021	29,7
160	212	0,171	50,1
161	141	0,008	19,7
161	213	0,046	31,7
162	142	0,005	17,0
162	214	0,036	26,9
163	143	0,004	14,0
163	215	0,025	22,8
164	144	0,001	13,7
164	216	0,010	24,0
165	145	0,000	8,2
165	217	0,002	13,8
166	146	0,000	8,6
166	218	0,003	14,3
167	147	0,006	19,1

167	219	0,034	30,6
168	148	0,005	17,1
168	220	0,030	27,0
177	157	0,004	14,6
177	229	0,004	14,6
178	158	0,004	14,6
178	230	0,004	14,6
179	159	0,001	11,7
179	231	0,001	11,7
180	160	0,002	11,1
180	232	0,002	11,1
181	161	0,001	6,7
181	233	0,001	6,7
182	162	0,001	8,1
182	259	0,001	8,1
183	188	0,005	14,9
183	260	0,005	14,9
184	189	0,005	14,6
184	261	0,005	14,6
185	190	0,004	11,6
185	262	0,002	9,7
186	191	0,005	19,5
186	263	0,003	16,5
187	192	0,001	15,0
187	264	0,000	12,6
188	193	0,002	11,9
188	265	0,001	10,0
189	194	0,001	12,5
189	266	0,001	10,6
190	195	0,001	11,0
190	267	0,000	9,3
191	196	0,005	12,0
191	268	0,002	10,1
192	197	0,007	19,3
192	269	0,004	16,3
193	198	0,003	16,5
193	270	0,003	16,5
194	199	0,004	26,8
194	271	0,004	26,8
195	200	0,001	21,2
195	272	0,001	21,2
196	201	0,002	18,3
196	273	0,002	18,3
197	202	0,000	17,3
197	274	0,000	17,3
198	203	0,000	15,9
198	275	0,000	15,9
199	204	0,002	16,6
199	276	0,002	16,6
200	205	0,003	26,7
200	277	0,003	26,7

201	206	0,005	25,1
201	278	0,001	17,7
202	207	0,003	20,4
202	279	0,001	14,4
203	208	0,003	17,6
203	280	0,001	12,5
204	209	0,001	18,8
204	281	0,000	13,1
205	210	0,000	14,4
205	282	0,000	10,3
206	211	0,001	17,5
206	283	0,000	12,5
207	212	0,003	24,8
207	284	0,001	17,4
208	213	0,003	20,4
208	285	0,001	14,4
209	214	0,008	20,4
209	286	0,008	20,4
210	215	0,008	23,4
210	287	0,008	23,4
211	216	0,003	18,4
211	288	0,003	18,4
212	217	0,002	14,9
212	289	0,002	14,9
213	218	0,001	9,8
213	290	0,001	9,8
214	219	0,001	11,1
214	291	0,001	11,1
215	220	0,006	20,6
215	292	0,006	20,6
216	259	0,006	23,5
216	188	0,006	23,5
217	260	0,007	23,5
217	189	0,002	16,4
218	261	0,012	25,9
218	190	0,003	18,2
219	262	0,003	18,5
219	191	0,001	13,0
220	263	0,005	17,2
220	192	0,002	12,1
221	264	0,001	16,9
221	193	0,000	12,1
222	265	0,001	13,7
222	194	0,000	9,8
223	266	0,005	23,3
223	195	0,001	16,4
224	267	0,010	25,6
224	196	0,003	18,0
225	268	0,001	12,2
225	197	0,001	12,2
226	269	0,004	16,6

226	198	0,004	16,6
227	270	0,000	12,1
227	199	0,000	12,1
228	271	0,002	9,4
228	200	0,002	9,4
229	272	0,000	10,3
229	201	0,000	10,3
230	273	0,000	8,1
230	202	0,000	8,1
231	274	0,001	12,5
231	203	0,001	12,5
232	275	0,004	16,0
232	204	0,004	16,0
233	276	0,002	15,6
233	205	0,001	12,1
234	277	0,002	16,4
234	206	0,001	12,8
235	278	0,001	11,9
235	207	0,000	9,3
236	279	0,000	11,0
236	208	0,000	8,1
237	280	0,000	8,0
237	209	0,000	6,3
238	281	0,000	10,3
238	210	0,000	8,0
239	282	0,002	15,1
239	211	0,001	11,6
240	283	0,002	16,3
240	212	0,001	12,7

Appendix C – Jacket nodes' position

Table 11 – Jacket nodes position, X,Y,Z

Node_ID	x	y	z
1	-15,00	-15,00	0,04
2	15,00	-15,00	0,04
3	15,00	15,00	0,04
4	-15,00	15,00	0,04
5	-14,80	-14,80	2,25
6	14,80	-14,80	2,25
7	14,80	14,80	2,25
8	-14,80	14,80	2,25
9	-14,74	-14,74	2,94
10	14,74	-14,74	2,94
11	14,74	14,74	2,94
12	-14,74	14,74	2,94
13	-13,62	-13,62	15,54
14	13,62	-13,62	15,54
15	13,62	13,62	15,54
16	-13,62	13,62	15,54
17	-13,56	-13,56	16,23
18	13,56	-13,56	16,23
19	13,56	13,56	16,23
20	-13,56	13,56	16,23
21	-12,43	-12,43	28,83
22	12,43	-12,43	28,83
23	12,43	12,43	28,83
24	-12,43	12,43	28,83
25	-12,37	-12,37	29,52
26	12,37	-12,37	29,52
27	12,37	12,37	29,52
28	-12,37	12,37	29,52
29	-11,25	-11,25	42,12
30	11,25	-11,25	42,12
31	11,25	11,25	42,12
32	-11,25	11,25	42,12
33	-11,19	-11,19	42,81
34	11,19	-11,19	42,81
35	11,19	11,19	42,81
36	-11,19	11,19	42,81
37	-10,06	-10,06	55,41
38	10,06	-10,06	55,41
39	10,06	10,06	55,41
40	-10,06	10,06	55,41

41	-10,00	-10,00	56,10
42	10,00	-10,00	56,10
43	10,00	10,00	56,10
44	-10,00	10,00	56,10
45	0,00	-14,16	9,49
46	14,16	0,00	9,49
47	0,00	14,16	9,49
48	-14,16	0,00	9,49
49	0,00	-12,97	22,80
50	12,97	0,00	22,80
51	0,00	12,97	22,80
52	-12,97	0,00	22,80
53	0,00	-11,78	36,12
54	11,78	0,00	36,12
55	0,00	11,78	36,12
56	-11,78	0,00	36,12
57	0,00	-10,60	49,44
58	10,60	0,00	49,44
59	0,00	10,60	49,44
60	-10,60	0,00	49,44
61	-14,97	-14,97	0,39
62	14,97	-14,97	0,39
63	14,97	14,97	0,39
64	-14,97	14,97	0,39
65	-14,57	-14,57	4,81
66	14,57	-14,57	4,81
67	14,57	14,57	4,81
68	-14,57	14,57	4,81
69	-13,78	-13,78	13,68
70	13,78	-13,78	13,68
71	13,78	13,78	13,68
72	-13,78	13,78	13,68
73	-13,39	-13,39	18,10
74	13,39	-13,39	18,10
75	13,39	13,39	18,10
76	-13,39	13,39	18,10
77	-12,60	-12,60	26,97
78	12,60	-12,60	26,97
79	12,60	12,60	26,97
80	-12,60	12,60	26,97
81	-12,20	-12,20	31,38
82	12,20	-12,20	31,38
83	12,20	12,20	31,38
84	-12,20	12,20	31,38

85	-11,41	-11,41	40,25
86	11,41	-11,41	40,25
87	11,41	11,41	40,25
88	-11,41	11,41	40,25
89	-11,02	-11,02	44,67
90	11,02	-11,02	44,67
91	11,02	11,02	44,67
92	-11,02	11,02	44,67
93	-10,40	-10,40	51,68
94	10,40	-10,40	51,68
95	10,40	10,40	51,68
96	-10,40	10,40	51,68
97	-13,35	-14,80	2,25
98	13,35	-14,80	2,25
99	14,80	-13,35	2,25
100	14,80	13,35	2,25
101	13,35	14,80	2,25
102	-13,35	14,80	2,25
103	-14,80	13,35	2,25
104	-14,80	-13,35	2,25
105	-13,41	-14,69	3,53
106	13,41	-14,69	3,53
107	14,69	-13,41	3,53
108	14,69	13,41	3,53
109	13,41	14,69	3,53
110	-13,41	14,69	3,53
111	-14,69	13,41	3,53
112	-14,69	-13,41	3,53
113	-12,29	-13,67	14,95
114	12,29	-13,67	14,95
115	13,67	-12,29	14,95
116	13,67	12,29	14,95
117	12,29	13,67	14,95
118	-12,29	13,67	14,95
119	-13,67	12,29	14,95
120	-13,67	-12,29	14,95
121	-12,25	-13,50	16,87
122	12,25	-13,50	16,87
123	13,50	-12,25	16,87
124	13,50	12,25	16,87
125	12,25	13,50	16,87
126	-12,25	13,50	16,87
127	-13,50	12,25	16,87
128	-13,50	-12,25	16,87

129	-11,13	-12,49	28,20
130	11,13	-12,49	28,20
131	12,49	-11,13	28,20
132	12,49	11,13	28,20
133	11,13	12,49	28,20
134	-11,13	12,49	28,20
135	-12,49	11,13	28,20
136	-12,49	-11,13	28,20
137	-11,09	-12,31	30,20
138	11,09	-12,31	30,20
139	12,31	-11,09	30,20
140	12,31	11,09	30,20
141	11,09	12,31	30,20
142	-11,09	12,31	30,20
143	-12,31	11,09	30,20
144	-12,31	-11,09	30,20
145	-9,97	-11,31	41,43
146	9,97	-11,31	41,43
147	11,31	-9,97	41,43
148	11,31	9,97	41,43
149	9,97	11,31	41,43
150	-9,97	11,31	41,43
151	-11,31	9,97	41,43
152	-11,31	-9,97	41,43
153	-9,94	-11,12	43,55
154	9,94	-11,12	43,55
155	11,12	-9,94	43,55
156	11,12	9,94	43,55
157	9,94	11,12	43,55
158	-9,94	11,12	43,55
159	-11,12	9,94	43,55
160	-11,12	-9,94	43,55
161	-8,82	-10,13	54,67
162	8,82	-10,13	54,67
163	10,13	-8,82	54,67
164	10,13	8,82	54,67
165	8,82	10,13	54,67
166	-8,82	10,13	54,67
167	-10,13	8,82	54,67
168	-10,13	-8,82	54,67
169	-8,55	-10,00	56,10
170	8,55	-10,00	56,10
171	10,00	-8,55	56,10
172	10,00	8,55	56,10

173	8,55	10,00	56,10
174	-8,55	10,00	56,10
175	-10,00	8,55	56,10
176	-10,00	-8,55	56,10
177	-0,93	-14,19	9,08
178	0,93	-14,19	9,08
179	14,19	-0,93	9,08
180	14,19	0,93	9,08
181	0,93	14,19	9,08
182	-0,93	14,19	9,08
183	-14,19	0,93	9,08
184	-14,19	-0,93	9,08
185	-0,93	-14,12	9,90
186	0,93	-14,12	9,90
187	14,12	-0,93	9,90
188	14,12	0,93	9,90
189	0,93	14,12	9,90
190	-0,93	14,12	9,90
191	-14,12	0,93	9,90
192	-14,12	-0,93	9,90
193	-0,65	-13,00	22,49
194	0,65	-13,00	22,49
195	13,00	-0,65	22,49
196	13,00	0,65	22,49
197	0,65	13,00	22,49
198	-0,65	13,00	22,49
199	-13,00	0,65	22,49
200	-13,00	-0,65	22,49
201	-0,65	-12,94	23,12
202	0,65	-12,94	23,12
203	12,94	-0,65	23,12
204	12,94	0,65	23,12
205	0,65	12,94	23,12
206	-0,65	12,94	23,12
207	-12,94	0,65	23,12
208	-12,94	-0,65	23,12
209	-0,64	-11,81	35,78
210	0,64	-11,81	35,78
211	11,81	-0,64	35,78
212	11,81	0,64	35,78
213	0,64	11,81	35,78
214	-0,64	11,81	35,78
215	-11,81	0,64	35,78
216	-11,81	-0,64	35,78

217	-0,64	-11,75	36,46
218	0,64	-11,75	36,46
219	11,75	-0,64	36,46
220	11,75	0,64	36,46
221	0,64	11,75	36,46
222	-0,64	11,75	36,46
223	-11,75	0,64	36,46
224	-11,75	-0,64	36,46
225	-0,75	-10,63	49,00
226	0,75	-10,63	49,00
227	10,63	-0,75	49,00
228	10,63	0,75	49,00
229	0,75	10,63	49,00
230	-0,75	10,63	49,00
231	-10,63	0,75	49,00
232	-10,63	-0,75	49,00
233	-0,75	-10,56	49,88
234	0,75	-10,56	49,88
235	10,56	-0,75	49,88
236	10,56	0,75	49,88
237	0,75	10,56	49,88
238	-0,75	10,56	49,88
239	-10,56	0,75	49,88
240	-10,56	-0,75	49,88
241	-15,00	-15,00	0,00
242	15,00	-15,00	0,00
243	15,00	15,00	0,00
244	-15,00	15,00	0,00